

ELECTRONIC INTERPRETATION OF ORGANIC CHEMISTRY. EFFECT OF SUBSTITUENTS ON THE STRENGTH OF ORGANIC BASES

BY SANTI K. PALIT

It is suggested that the weakness of ammonia as a base arises out of the positive charge on its three hydrogen atoms which repels the approaching hydrogen-ion in the conventional base strength determination.

Any substitution of one or two hydrogens by alkyl groups increases the base strength since the repulsion factor is decreased. This is helped by the weak electron-donating (+I) nature of the alkyl groups which tends to increase the base strength by purely inductive way. The decrease of base strength on passing from a secondary to a tertiary base, is ascribed to steric factors. Based on this picture a consistent interpretation of the strength of all organic bases including the indicators is made.

The nature of the steric factor is analysed and shown to be composed of at least three independent effects. The first is the size and shape of the alkyl group; the second is the spatial interference by the methyl and of the alkyl chain with the free electron pair. The third is ascribed to a basic chemical fact, first hinted at by Pauling, that a N-C bond is inherently inferior to a N-H bond in its power of capturing a positive charge (here, H⁺ ion) owing to carbon being more electronegative than hydrogen.

It is shown that if the bases are compared against an uncharged acid like boron trialkyl, the order of the base strength should be different as the strong electrical effects are absent, and the experimental results so far available are found to be in agreement with what should be expected from the above viewpoint.

The effect of substituents on the strength of organic acids is fairly well understood from the electronic mechanism (cf. Dippy, *Chem. Rev.*, 1939, 25, 151; Branch and Calvin, "Theory of Organic Chemistry", 1945). A thorough discussion of base strength from a similar standpoint has never been attempted, though it is recognized in almost all current writings on the subject *e.g.*, by Watson ("Modern Theories of Organic Chemistry", 2nd Ed., 1937), Pauling ("Nature of Chemical Bond", 2nd Ed., 1940), Wheland ("Theory of Resonance", 1944) and others, that the bases should in principle be subject to a similar treatment. However, a systematic discussion of base strength is met with great difficulty because even the similar bases behave rather anomalously. We cite below two examples to illustrate our point.

As opposed to the behaviour of acids, we should expect the base strength to decrease by the introduction of an electron-attracting (-I) group and to increase by the introduction of an electron-releasing (+I) group. However, the experimental values do not always support such conclusions and very irregular results are often obtained. For example, since alkyl groups are weakly electron-repelling in the order: propyl > ethyl > methyl in their purely inductive effect, we should expect the monoalkylamines to be

Previous two publications in this series are: I. *J. Org. Chem.*, 1947, 12, 752; II. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1947, 51, 837, and a very short note on the theme of the present publication, 1947, 51, 1028.

slightly stronger than ammonia in the above order. However, the experimentally observed order for the base strength of the monoalkylamines and ammonia is ethyl > n-propyl > methyl > ammonia, all the monoalkylamines being more than 25 times as strong as ammonia. The second anomalous point to note is that though the introduction of an alkyl group in ammonia increases its strength rather very strongly, the introduction of an alkyl group to a secondary amine to convert it into a tertiary amine depresses its strength considerably. Thus, ethylamine is about 30 times stronger than ammonia but triethylamine is only about half as strong as diethylamine.

Brown (*Science*, 1946, 103, 385) has attempted to theorize on the subject based on experimental studies on the reaction between boron trialkyls and the amines. Brown (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 1452) rejects the thermodynamic dissociation constants of bases in aqueous solution as a measure of base strength attributing them as due to "complex solvation effects the importance of which cannot yet be estimated" and takes the strength of binding between a base and a boron trialkyl as a more correct measure of the base strength.

The purpose of the present paper is to suggest a new approach, based on classical concepts, which removes the apparent anomalies as mentioned above, and reconciles Brown's theory and his results with the question of base strength in aqueous solution.

The Problem of Base Strength of Ammonia

Since nitrogen is strongly electronegative, we should expect that the binding electron pairs in all N:H bonds in ammonia will be drawn closer to nitrogen away from the hydrogen atoms polarizing each N:H bond. As a result of this each of the three hydrogen atoms in ammonia will acquire a weak positive charge (Palmer, "Valency: Classical and Modern", 1944, pp. 132, 128; Pauling, *loc. cit.*). Any approaching hydrogen ion is attracted by the unshared pair of electrons but is repelled by the three positively charged hydrogen atoms round the nitrogen, as a result of which ammonia behaves as a weak base. However, if one or more of the hydrogens in ammonia are replaced by groups, the strength of the resulting base will depend on three factors:—

(i) The classical polar factors *i.e.*, the electron-donating (+I, or +T), or electron attracting (−I, −T) power* of the replacing groups.

(ii) The repulsion between the remaining hydrogen atoms round the central nitrogen atom and the approaching acid (here, the hydrogen-ion), which might be called the repulsion factor.

(iii) The availability of the unshared pair of electrons as influenced by the steric interference between the unshared pair of electrons and the alkyl group present round the central nitrogen atom.

This is the same as the classical "steric factor" and has been given a special name by Brown as B-strain.

* The notation of I and T effects and the nomenclature used in this paper are from Remick's "Electronic Interpretation of Organic Chemistry", John Wiley, 1943.

So, in simple compounds, where only the polar factor is operative or is too strong in comparison with the other factors, on substitution of any of the hydrogen atoms in ammonia by an electron-attracting group, a reduction of base strength will occur. Thus, hydroxylamines and hydrazine are found to be much weaker than ammonia (Table I). However, in most cases the phenomena will be complicated by the operation of the other factors and this will be discussed in what follows.

Alkyl Amines

The first factor which depends on the inductive effect is known to be very weak with alkyl groups, and hence can be neglected, or included along with the second factor whose effect is in the same sense, and so, the effects due to the second and the third factors need only be considered in the case of the aliphatic amines. These two effects generally act in opposite directions with the alkylamines, the first two factors tending to decrease it as we progressively replace the hydrogens of ammonia with alkyl group. For example, if a hydrogen atom in ammonia is replaced by an ethyl group, the second factor, which arises from the repulsion of the approaching hydrogen ion by the three positively charged hydrogen atoms in ammonia, will now tend to augment the strength. The approaching hydrogen-ion will now undergo repulsion only by two hydrogen atoms which are not symmetrically situated round its line of approach. This diminution of the repulsion to the approaching hydrogen-ion will cause an increase in the strength of the base in comparison to ammonia.

The second factor, which is a direct electrical repulsion effect, generally takes precedence and so ethylamine is found to be 30 times stronger than ammonia. The increment of strength, when we pass to diethylamine, is less (about 20 times) as the compensating steric factor is increasing. On passing to triethylamine, the steric factor is enough to compensate for the direct repulsion effect and actually a decrease in strength by a factor $\frac{1}{2}$ is observed. Hence, it appears that a balance between the two opposing factors is reached at the secondary amine which is therefore the strongest base in a given series of amines produced by successive replacement of the hydrogens in ammonia by a weakly inductive group. This behaviour seems to be characteristic of all alkylamines, as will be seen from Table I, where we always get a monotonic increase of strength up to the secondary amine, followed by a sharp drop in basicity on passing to the tertiary amine.

In comparing methylamines with ethylamines it is evident that all the above factors are operating in about the same way except that for the polar factors, methyl groups being less electron-donating (+I) than ethyl group. This accounts for the order: ethylamines > methylamines (Table I). On passing to propyl and butylamines, however, we should expect the strength to increase slightly but continuously, if the polar factor was only operative, but strong steric interference comes into play owing to the end of the long hydrocarbon chain approaching the lone electron pair, which more than compensates for the polar factor. This accounts for the order: ethylamines > propylamines or butylamines. This also elucidates the peculiar fact noted by various investigators "that the ethyl group is the most basic (base-producing) of all the alkyl groups" (Watson, *loc cit.*).

TABLE I

Dissociation constants of aliphatic amines (28°).

Base.	K_1 .	Ref.	Base.	K_b .	Ref.
Ammonia	1.79×10^{-6}	a	n-Propylamine	3.9×10^{-4}	c
Hydroxylamine	1.07×10^{-8}	b	Di-n-propylamine	8.2×10^{-4}	a
Hydrazine	1.5×10^{-6} (20°)	b	Tri-n-propylamine	4.5×10^{-4}	c
Methylamine	4.38×10^{-4}	a	n-Butylamine	4.09×10^{-4}	d
Dimethylamine	5.2×10^{-4}	a	Di-n-butylamine	2.05×10^{-3}	d
Trimethylamine	5.45×10^{-5}	a	Tri-n-butylamine	8.55×10^{-5}	d
Ethylamine	4.6×10^{-4}	c	isoButylamine	2.6×10^{-4}	c
Diethylamine	1.01×10^{-3}	c	Di-isobutylamine	3.9×10^{-4}	c
Triethylamine	5.2×10^{-4}	c	Tri-isobutylamine	2.1×10^{-4}	c

(a) Harned and Owen, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **52**, 5079.

(b) Landolt-Bornstein Tabellen, 5th Ed., 2nd Supplement, p. 1093

(c) International Critical Tables, Vol. VI, p. 259 (1929).

(d) Hall, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, **54**, 3469.

Peculiarity of the Methyl Group.—The methylamines are weaker than ethylamines not only because the methyl group is less electron-donating than the ethyl group, but also because the methyl group is itself a repellant for hydrogen-ion, as all the three hydrogen atoms become comparatively positive as a result of electron-drainage possibly owing to easy polarisability of the CH bonds in the methyl group. There is a pronounced relative retardation of strength at every step as we pass stepwise from ammonia to trimethylamine as compared to passing from ammonia to triethylamine. The author thinks that this peculiarity of the methyl group to behave as a weak positively charged centre and so, to be able to repel hydrogen-ion in comparison to other alkyl groups is considerably responsible for the above trend and a few other anomalies encountered with the methyl group.

It should be noted that neither the steric factor nor the direct repulsion should change uniformly with gradual replacement of the hydrogens in ammonia by alkyl groups. The repulsion factor of the three hydrogens is most affected by the first replacement, since the symmetrical disposition of the three centres of repulsion is destroyed and the remaining hydrogen atoms in the N-H bonds are less polarised, whereas the steric factor is the strongest at the third replacement, because this creates the maximum crowding of the big alkyl groups round the basic electron pair. This causes the increase of base strength in passing from ammonia to a primary amine and the decrease in passing from a secondary to a tertiary to be generally very large.

Mechanism of the Steric Factor

The mechanism of steric hindrance to the approaching hydrogen-ion by say the propyl group in propylamine, which makes it a weaker base than ethylamine, may not be pure space factor only, and an interesting suggestion made by Bennett and Moses (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 2361) and also by Dippy (*loc. cit.*) to explain the abnormally high

strength of butyric acid in comparison with the series of straight-chain fatty acids is well worth keeping in mind. It might well be possible that the mobility of the hydrocarbon chain causes its methyl end to come near to the unshared pair of electron to give an extra shielding effect.

We should like to point out another important factor, which is rather electrochemical in origin and often plays the most important role among all the possible factors which we have labelled together as 'steric'. Carbon being negative to hydrogen and N-C bond being less polarisable than a N-H bond, whenever a hydrogen atom of ammonia or an amine is replaced by an alkyl group, the new C-N bond reduces the receptive power of the nitrogen for an approaching hydrogen-ion tending to make the resulting base weaker. It is quite possible that this factor might be the chief cause of reducing the strength of an aliphatic tertiary amine in comparison with the corresponding secondary amine. However, we believe all the above factors, classed together as 'steric,' to operate and we need not single out any of them as the most important unless we have definite physical data to support our contention.

We would like to call this restrictive effect originating from the polar nature of the atoms by a special name and we propose the term "polar-striction effect". This idea of what we have called "polarstriction effect" is not wholly our own. A similar restrictive effect on the operation of resonance involving formal positive charges on nitrogen attached to a carbon has been postulated by Pauling (*loc. cit.*, p. 213) to explain the peculiar reduction of base strength of N-N'-dialkyl substituted guanidines. We believe this principle to be of wide applicability and shall see later how it causes the strength of an aromatic secondary base to increase on being converted into a tertiary one, as opposed to the behaviour of the aliphatic bases.

Cyclic Amines

According to the above considerations any compound, RNH_2 , will be stronger than ammonia as long as R has only the electron-releasing or weak electron-attracting power. On the contrary, if R has a very strong electron-attracting power, the polar factor, which is no longer negligible, might more than compensate for the reduced repulsion effect. Since strong electron-drainage is a rule with resonance or tautomeric effect ($-T$), the very weak base strengths of aniline, pyrrole, pyridine and quinoline are easily understandable (Table II). This is, of course, the generally accepted opinion. With respect to pyridine and quinoline, the tautomeric effect, as shown below, is stronger in quinoline than in pyridine as it plays over a much longer conjugation and this makes quinoline weaker than pyridine.

Pyridine

Quinoline

In passing, it might be noted that the electron-drainage effect ($-T$) of the phenyl group is so strong that diphenylamine has practically no basic power. As soon as the strong electron-attracting power owing to the tautomeric ($-T$) effect in the above compounds is destroyed by reduction of the double bonds, the resulting compounds, *cyclohexylamine* and *piperidine*, become strong bases, much stronger than ammonia (Table II).

TABLE II
Dissociation constant of cyclic bases (25°).

Base.	Formula.	K_b .	Ref.
Aniline	$C_6H_5NH_2$	3.82×10^{-10}	a
Pyridine	C_5H_5N	1.71×10^{-9}	a
Quinoline	C_8H_7N	6.3×10^{-10}	a
Pyrrrole	C_4H_4NH	ca. 10^{-10} or lower	b, c
<i>cycloHexylamine</i>	$C_6H_{11}NH_2$	4.39×10^{-4}	a
Piperidine	$C_5H_{10}NH$	1.25×10^{-3}	d
Pyrrrolidine	C_4H_8NH	1.3×10^{-3}	

(a) Landolt—Bornstein, *Physikalisch-Chemische Tabellen*, 5th Edition, 1936, 3rd Supplement, 3rd Part, p. 2121.

(d) Wheland, "Theory of Resonance," John Wiley, p. 178 (1944).

(c) Palmer, "Valency: Classical and Modern", Cambridge University Press, 1944, p. 210.

(d) International Critical Tables, Vol. VI, p. 259 (1929)

N-Substituted Aromatic Bases

The substituted anilines show a slightly different behaviour from that of the alkyl amines. Since the extreme weakness of aniline is due to a resonance or tautomeric effect of the phenyl ring, the N-C bond will have a partial double bond character. Any substitution in the N- position by an alkyl group, will tend to interfere with the above resonance or partial double bond character, because such a resonance tends to put a formal positive charge on the nitrogen atom which acts against the natural electronegativity of the N-C bond in the nitrogen—alkyl attachment. Hence, the resonance will fall off continuously as alkyl groups are progressively substituted in the N-position in aniline, which will therefore cause a progressive increase of base strength by such replacement. As a result, the strength continuously increases as each of the hydrogens is progressively replaced by alkyl groups. This accounts for the observed order: dialkylaniline > monoalkyl aniline > aniline (Table III). Further, as explained previously, we get the order: ethylanilines > methylanilines. Also, propyl groups have a stronger steric influence than ethyl groups and this accounts for the observed order: ethylanilines > propylanilines. Since resonance plays little or no part in the basicity of benzylamine, we shall expect it to have base strength similar to the aliphatic behaviour and not to aniline. These expectations are realised experimentally as will be observed in Table III that it is stronger than ammonia and its dimethyl derivative is weaker than the monomethyl derivative.

TABLE III

Base strength of *N*-substituted aromatic bases (25°).
 ($pK_a = -\log_{10} K_w / K_b$.)

Base.	pK_a .	Ref.	Base.	K_b .	Ref.
Aniline	4.62	<i>a</i>	<i>Di-n</i> -propylaniline	5.59	<i>a</i>
Methylaniline	4.85	<i>a</i>	Benzylamine	2.35×10^{-5}	<i>b</i>
Dimethylaniline	5.06	<i>a</i>	Methylbenzylamine	3.80×10^{-5}	<i>b</i>
Ethylaniline	5.11	<i>a</i>	Dimethylbenzylamine	8.5×10^{-6}	<i>c</i>
Diethylaniline	6.56	<i>a</i>	Ethylbenzylamine	4.75×10^{-5}	<i>b</i>
<i>n</i> -Propylaniline	5.02	<i>a</i>	Diethylbenzylamine	3.0×10^{-5}	<i>c</i>

(a) Hall and Sprinkle, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, **55**, 3469.

(b) Carothers, Bickford and Hurwitz, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **49**, 2908.

(c) International Critical Tables, Vol. VI, p. 260 (1929).

Nuclear-substituted Bases

If the substituted methyl group is introduced in the ring instead of in the *N*-position, it affects the base strength according to its position. In the *para* position, its strong electron-donation arising out of its hyper-conjugative effect is transmitted to the basic electron-pair across the ring to make the base much stronger. In the *meta* position, the electron-donation is very weak as no resonance can interplay and accordingly the base strength is very slightly increased. Hence, we should expect the order: *para* > *meta* > original base. This is the actually observed order with methylanilines as will be seen from Table IV.

It is very difficult to say anything with certainty about the *ortho* position owing to the well known unpredictable "*ortho*-effect", which here arises from at least two separate causes; one is the tautomeric effect of the ring and the other is the direct spatial interference by the group in the *ortho* position. In the case of a strong electron-attracting group ($-T$), such as the nitro group, both the above factors act in the same direction to reduce the strength and so, we get the order: *ortho* < original base. This is exemplified by the data for nitroanilines in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Base strength of nuclear-substituted aromatic bases (25°).

Original base.	Substituent.	Position of the substituent.	pK_a .	K_b	Ref.
Aniline	None	—	4.62	5.7×10^{-10}	<i>a</i>
,	Methyl (CH ₃)	Ortho	4.39		<i>a</i>
"	"	Meta	4.69		<i>a</i>
"	"	Para	5.12		<i>a</i>
"	Nitro (NO ₂)	Ortho		5.6×10^{-13}	<i>b</i>
"	"	Meta		4.0×10^{-12}	<i>b</i>
"	"	Para		1.0×10^{-13}	<i>b</i>

TABLE IV (contd.)

Original base.	Substituent	Position of the substituent.	pK_{H} .	K_{b}	Ref.
Benzylamine	None	—		2.3×10^{-5}	c
"	Methyl (CH_3)	Ortho		1.70×10^{-5}	c
"	"	Meta		2.40×10^{-5}	c
"	"	Para		2.55×10^{-5}	c

(a) Hall and Sprinkle, *loc. cit.*

(d) Landolt-Bornstein Tables, 5th Ed, 2nd Supplement, p. 1093.

(c) Carothers, Bickford and Hurwitz, *loc. cit.*

Nuclear-substituted benzylamines behave exactly as discussed above in the case of aniline except that the interference owing to the *ortho*-effect is here stronger owing to the possibility of a six-membered ring formation.

Guanidine Bases

A direct consequence of our point of view is that compounds of the guanidine type, $(\text{NH}_2)_2\text{C}=\text{NH}$ should be very strong bases because all the factors which go to increase the base strength are very favourable. There is very little or no steric effect round the basic nitrogen atom ($=\text{NH}$) as it is connected by a double bond to the carbon atom. Also, the tautomeric effect, if it acts at all, will act in favour of the nitrogen atom in the $\text{C}=\text{N}$ bond making the nitrogen atom richer in electrons. All these factors contribute to make guanidines and amidines strong bases. An opposite state of affair exists in the ureas $(\text{NH}_2)_2\text{C}=\text{O}$ and amides $\text{R}.\text{CONH}_2$. The tautomeric flow of electrons owing to the $\text{C}\equiv\text{O}$ group is away from the nitrogen, which together make these compounds extremely weak bases.

Indicator Bases

The same considerations apply to indicator bases and it is possible to predict and interpret the change of indicator range with change of structure. Since the colour change of an indicator is due to the addition of a hydrogen-ion either to the indicator base or to the anion of the indicator acid acting as the base, we can apply the above considerations of base strength to all indicators. A stronger base requires less H-ion concentrations (higher p_{H}) in order to be converted into its conjugate acid: in other words, *the stronger an indicator base, the higher is its p_{H} range of colour change.*

The effect of alkyl groups can be exemplified with well-known indicators. For example, taking methyl orange and ethyl orange it follows from our foregoing discussions that the ethyl compound will be a stronger base. We should therefore expect ethyl orange to require less H-ion concentration (higher p_{H}) to convert it into its acid form, which is experimentally found to be true (Table V).

It should be noted that the basic atom in the common indicators is either the negatively charged oxygen (as in phthaleins) or the neutral nitrogen (as in the azo indicators). Evidently, it will be easier to add a H-ion to a negatively charged oxygen than to a

neutral nitrogen. Hence, we find that the indicator ranges of phthaleines are generally in the alkaline side, whereas the azo indicators occupy the acid region.

It will also be observed that when a carboxylate is converted into a sulphonate (as for example, compare phenolphthalein and phenol red, or *o*-cresolphthalein and cresol red), the latter has a lower p_H *i. e.*, it is a weaker base. This is easily understandable as we should expect a sulphonate ion to be more electron-attracting than a carboxylate ion, the former thus reducing the availability of the basic electron-pair.

The substitution of a methyl group in a phenolate-type base is free from '*ortho*-effect' and increases the base strength as is seen from the fact that cresols including *ortho*-cresols are stronger bases (weaker acids) than phenol. Probably, the strong electrical attraction between the negatively charged base and the phenol overcomes the disturbing *ortho*-effect. In conformity with this, the indicators, which are *ortho*-cresol derivatives, have a definitely higher p_H range than the similar ones derived from phenol (see Table V, data for 5 and 6, 7 and 8, and 9 & 10).

TABLE V

Colour change interval of indicators.

No.	Common name.	Scientific name.	Transformation interval, p_H	Ref.
1	Methyl orange	Sodium dimethylaminoazobenzene sulphonate	3.1—4.4	b a
2	Ethyl orange	Sodium diethylaminoazobenzene sulphonate	3.5—4.5	b a
3	Methyl red	Dimethylaminoazobenzene carboxylic acid	4.3—6.3	a
4	Propyl red	Dipropylaminoazobenzene carboxylic acid	4.6—6.6	b
5	Phenolphthalein		8.0—9.8	b
6	<i>o</i> -Cresolphthalein	<i>o</i> -Methyl derivative of No. 5	8.2—9.8	"
7	Phenolbenzein (Aurin, rosolic acid)	Benzoic acid analogue of No. 5	6.0—7.6	"
8	<i>o</i> -Cresolbenzein	<i>o</i> -Methyl derivative of No. 7	7.2—8.6	"
9	Phenol red	Phenol sulphonphthalein	6.4—8.2	"
10	Cresol red	<i>o</i> -Cresolsulphonphthalein	7.0—8.8	"
11	Chlorophenol red	Dichloro derivative of No. 9	4.8—6.4	"
12	Bromophenol blue	Tetrabromo derivative of No. 9	3.0—4.6	"
13	Bromocresol purple	Dibromo derivative of No. 10	7.0—8.8	"
14	Dibromo- <i>o</i> -cresolbenzein	Dibromo derivative of No. 8	5.2—6.8	"
15	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenol		6.5—8.5	"
16	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenol		3.0—7.6	"

TABLE V (contd.)

No	Common name.	Transformation interval, p_H .	Ref.
17	2 : 4-Dinitrophenol	2.0—4.7	b
18	2 : 5-Dinitrophenol	4.0—6.0	"
19	2 : 6-Dinitrophenol	1.7—4.4	"
20	2 : 4 : 6-Trinitrophenol	0.1—0.8	a
(a)	Table of Hydrogen Ion Concentration Ranges (p_H) and Color Changes, Eastman Organic Chemicals Co.		
(b)	Kolthoff, "Acid-base Indicators," translated by Rosenblum, Mollilen Co. (1937).		

The halogen substituted sulphonphthaleins behave as expected. In accordance with the fact that halogen substitution in the ring depresses the base strength considerably owing to simple inductive effect, all the chloro-, bromo- and iodo-sulphonphthaleins have their colour range at a much lower p_H than the parent compound.

Exactly similar considerations apply to the nitrophenol. The introduction of a nitro group into phenol will diminish the base strength and hence the nitrophenols should be weaker bases than phenol which is experimentally found to be true. Of the two nitrophenols, *meta* and *para*, the *para* will be the weaker owing to the tautomeric or resonance effect and in agreement with this, the colour change interval of *meta* is found to be at a higher p_H . The dinitrophenols (2 : 4, 2 : 5 and 2 : 6) should be weaker bases than mononitrophenols and so they should have a lower p_H range. Further, the *diortho* (2 : 4) compound is found to have a lower p_H range which is evidently due to the *ortho*-effect referred to. The trinitrophenols are expected to have a p_H range further lower down and it is observed that picric acid (2 : 4 : 6- trinitrophenol) changes colour at a very strongly acid region. The above are only illustrative examples, and various other indicators can be similarly treated to obtain a good correlation among them.

A very serious discrepancy between the expectations of our theory and reported data has been noticed. Bader in 1890 reported the values for the acid dissociation constants of cresols to be of the order of 10^{-8} and that of phenol of the order of 10^{-10} . Later measurements have confirmed the correct order of the data for phenol but no precise measurement of the value for cresol seems to have been carried out except by Boyd by hydrolytic method which is generally considered not too reliable. Boyd reports values of the order of 10^{-11} , which is in agreement with what we should expect. If Bader's data are correct, it seems that a methyl group can increase the acid dissociation constant *i. e.*, decrease the basic dissociation constant by a factor of 100. This seems to be very unusual and even opposite in sense to the expected direction of change. The matter evidently needs further careful experimentation.

Bases against Generalized Acids

If the approaching acid is not the positively charged hydrogen-ion, but a neutral molecule, *e. g.*, a boron trialkyl, the powerful electrical forces arising out of the charged hydrogen-ion become practically absent and the other factors begin to assume importance.

The base strength will be mainly dependent on the availability of the unshared pair but other factors, such as weaker electrical forces and steric factors should also play an important part. The success of Brown's theory lies in the interpretation of the base strength considered from the last standpoint, particularly as depending on the size of the groups around boron and nitrogen.

The main experimental finding of Brown is that the relative strength of the bases NH_3 , RNH_2 , R_2NH , and R_3N , measured against any acid BR'_3 , depends on the size of the R and R', and with increasing size of R and R', the order tends to become from one extreme $\text{NH}_3 < \text{RNH}_2 < \text{R}_2\text{NH} < \text{R}_3\text{N}$ (called A order), to the other extreme $\text{NH}_3 > \text{RNH}_2 > \text{R}_2\text{NH} > \text{R}_3\text{N}$ (called F order). All intermediate orders between A and F exist (A order has actually not been found so far) depending on the size of R and R' and they are designated as B, C, D and E. Brown finds, for example, that with the same acid, boron trimethyl, as we pass along methyl, ethyl, isopropyl and *ter*-butyl amines the order changes to B, D, E and F respectively.

Evidently, such a behaviour can be explained by any two opposing factors one of which would tend to increase the strength giving rise to the A order and the other to decrease the strength producing the F order as the hydrogen atoms in ammonia are successively replaced by alkyl groups. Since increasing the size of R and R' groups always tends to shift the relative base strength curve to a higher order, Brown unerringly identifies the latter factor as of steric origin, depending on the size of the alkyl groups which introduces a kind of strain in the acid and base molecules and also at the "interface" of their union. Brown suggests the first factor to be the classical polar factor which by acting in opposition with the steric factor, produces the observed order.

This straightforward and simple theory of Brown is capable of accounting for the observed factors. Our ideas in aqueous solution are also in agreement with this theory, and it is of interest to note that the order of the values is mutually consistent. For example, since the repulsion factor plays a minor role in the case of generalized acids and the polar factor of the alkyl group is rather weak, we should expect that the ratio of strengths between ammonia and any base, *e.g.* trimethylamine, when compared against any uncharged acid *e.g.*, triethyl boron, will be greater than the same ratio with hydrogen-ion as the reference acid. The least value recorded by Brown (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 67, 378) for the ratio of their dissociation constants against triethyl boron is $K_{\text{NH}_3} : K_{(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_3\text{B}}$ equal to $0.91 : 0.09 = 10.1$, whereas the ratio of their dissociation constants in water is about $1.79 : 5.45 = 0.33$. This shows clearly the importance of the charge of the acid against which the bases are compared and lends support to the bold assertion by Lewis (*J. Franklin Inst.*, 1938, 226, 293) of the non-existence of any monotonic series of base strength. In a recent book, Luder and Zuffanti "(Electronic Theory of Acids and Bases", McGraw Hill, 1946) have discussed the question from various angles. Trimethyl boron, if used in the above example as reference acid, behaves somewhat anomalously owing possibly to the anomalous nature of the methyl group, as referred to earlier.

We consider the general outline of Brown's theory to be substantially correct but would think that included in his steric factor is also the 'polarstriction effect' we have discussed before. This effect becomes particularly important as we proceed from a secondary to a tertiary amine. The tertiary amine has no hydrogen attached to the

nitrogen atom and so it has very much less tendency than a secondary amine to combine with a boron trialkyl, as such combination involves a formal positive charge on the nitrogen. We believe that this is the main reason for the fact observed by Brown that the tertiary amine is invariably weaker than the secondary amine though the relative strength of the other amines varies with the nature of the alkyl group.

A limitation of Brown's theory is that though it predicts the tendency towards change of the type of curve for a series of amines with change in the alkyl group, it is unable to compare the strength of any two amines against any acid. For example, this theory cannot say which of the two bases between trimethylamine and triethylamine is stronger. The only thing it definitely says is that ethylamines should have a higher order curve than the methylamines. This limitation will probably disappear when we know more about the steric factors in the alkyl groups to which Brown's important results have drawn our attention.

DEPARTMENT OF PHYSICAL CHEMISTRY,
INDIAN ASSOCIATION FOR THE CULTIVATION
OF SCIENCE, CALCUTTA 12.

Received September 3, 1947.